

Equivalent electrical circuit modeling of the irradiation and NBTS induced threshold voltage shift in p-channel power VDMOSFETs

Nikola Mitrović^{*1}, Sandra Veljković¹, Vojkan Davidović¹, Srboljub Stanković², Snežana Djorić-Veljković³, Emilija Živanović¹, Danijel Danković¹

¹ University of Niš, Faculty of Electronic Engineering, Niš, Serbia

² University of Belgrade, Institute of Nuclear Sciences Vinča, Belgrade, Serbia

³ University of Niš, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Niš, Serbia

<https://doi.org/10.21175/rad.abstr.book.2025.9.3>

Compact equivalent electrical circuit modeling is one of the types of modeling concrete device parameter shift in parameter dynamic surrounding. It is different from the physics based analytical modeling that centers around solving a big number of equations that describe certain processes or phenomena. Especially in surroundings where several types of different conditions (bias, temperature, radiation, humidity, magnetic field) are variable, solving particle-level equations can be a very demanding task, even for advanced simulators. Therefore, one of the approaches is to design a model that comprises of simpler Equivalent Electrical Circuit (EEC) and that will focus on a single device parameter, thereby reducing computational time for parameter modeling.

Irradiation of p-channel Metal Oxide Semiconductor devices (pMOS) devices degrades the threshold voltage, which is one of the most important operating parameters of MOS devices. Irradiation induced threshold voltage shift (ΔV_T) is noted also in the devices with greater oxide thickness, such as p-channel power Vertical Double-Diffused MOS devices (estimated oxide thickness is around 100 nm). Post irradiation Negative Bias Temperature Stressing (NBTS) leads to the partial recovery of the irradiation induced degradation, but is very dependent on the bias and temperature conditions. This paper gives insight into an EEC model that models both irradiation and NBTS induced threshold voltage shift.

The basis for modeling are experimental results. Samples for the experiment were commercial p-channel power VDMOSFETs IRF9520. Experiments consists of two phases, first one being the irradiation and the second one being NBTS. Irradiation was performed at the Metrological Laboratory at the Institute for Nuclear Sciences, Vinča, Serbia, using Co-60 radiation source. Samples were irradiated with the dose of 30 Gy, with the dose rate of 0.5 Gy/min. NBTS was performed at the laboratories of the Department of Microelectronics of the Faculty of Electronic Engineering, University of Niš, Serbia. During NBTS ($T = 175$ °C, $V_G = -50$ V), that lasted 168 h in the prespecified time intervals, transfer I-V characteristics in the saturation region were measured. Threshold voltage is determined from the I-V characteristics using the second derivative method. Absolute value of ΔV_T is exponentially increased during the irradiation and exponentially decreased during the NBTS.

Since ΔV_T changes exponentially, the central element of the CCE is capacitor. Increase of the ΔV_T is modeled as charging of the capacitor through condition determined resistance, while the decrease of the is modeled as discharging of the capacitor through NBTS conditions determined resistance. For the series of the experimental results values of EEC elements are calculated using Lagrange's theorem. Modeled results show correspondence with the experimental results, where relative error of modeling in all of the experimental phases is less than 18 %.

Keywords: modeling, VDMOSFET, irradiation, NBTS

Acknowledgment: This work has been supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Grant Number: 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200102] The authors would like to thank the staff of the Laboratory of Radiation and Environmental Protection, Institute "Vinča", for support. Part of this work has been supported by the Horizon Europe Twinning project AIDA4Edge (Grant Agreement No. 101160293).